

8T –Quantum Variantics

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Introduction

This paper is in depth analysis with the flaws of Quantum mechanics, by the author of the 8T, theory which unified the known interactions using variational manifolds, by doing so provided simple answer to several major unanswered questions, both in Quantum scale and in cosmological scales. Quantum mechanics is a set of ideas which derived by a set of experiments. While the experiments dictate the kind of equations and descriptions that are in the set of ideas. While one certainly cannot doubt what experiments indicate, it is possible to examine and improve the ideas which are describing reality, and in particular the methods, questions and equations. As Dirac once indicated that, there should be a more complete version of Quantum Mechanics. Let us begin with the flawed formulation.

First of all, the most obvious flaw in formulation is with the definition of "Energy". How can one solve equations in QM without a proper definition of "Energy"? The operator E and H does not mean anything, so it is possible to calculate with it, but understanding the meaning of energy is still not part of the current formulation of QM.

$$E\Psi(x, t) = \hat{H}\Psi(x, t)$$

This equation may be solvable but it is not clear, it's too abstract and it does not tell you anything about nature. One can argue that we know the definition of energy as to the summation of kinetic and potential. If so one must also ask, how does mass form, as there exist both mass positive and massless particles. And mass plays a role in the formulation of the kinetic and potential energy. Below is another example of the flawed formulation of Quantum mechanics.

$$\langle B | \hat{L} | A \rangle$$

Another dominating theme is the following transformations between two states by a linear operator. First of all, it's too abstract, and it does not tell you anything about nature, despite being solvable. What's the worth of calculating without understanding? This is what computers do. These things are solvable but they are telling very little in intuitive fashion. The authors of QM are not explaining why QM is described by linear operators rather than non-linear operators, which is another flaw in this formulation. Let alone the fact that it goes from right to left, rather than all equations from left to right. One must clarify that it is not a case against QM but a case against how QM is described. There is a difference. The questions concerning the issues of "why" are just as important as the questions concerning "what", the entire extrapolation of the primordial coupling series was built on the notion of "why". In QM there exist very little to no explanations of why things are the way they are and that another major flaw in the current formulation of Quantum mechanics. So the challenge in hand is first of all, given the recent advancements in the field of Theoretical physics, and the unification of the interactions using manifolds is to re-build the flawed QM by using axioms and mappings. From here on out, QM is considered old formulation, and QV is the new formulation, which stands for **Quantum Variantics**. The new formulation is of variational curvature which will aspire to build more complete analogs for the dominating themes of QM. The most urgent mapping that is lacking in the old formulation of Quantum mechanics, is the following map between Ricci flow to Energy, which meant to provide a clear and solid definition to "Energy".

$$\varphi: g \rightarrow E$$

The Schrodinger equation for the electron that is describing how does a non-vanishing curvature spike which has spin one half is moving across a nine-fold combination of two distinct elements which differ in sign. The electron has a superscript which describe the number of elements it contains. There is no need to use the Planck constant, which is a measurable constant. The problem with using this constant is that it is not a result of a variational principle. The equation with the Planck constant, has a flawed beauty for two reasons. First, it is not clear what it is. Second it is not clear why it has the value it has. Why that number and not another?

$$\Psi(M_\mu, t) = e^{(\partial g / \partial t)} \Psi(M_\mu, t_0)$$

Where the term in the exponential stands for:

$$\left(\frac{\partial g}{\partial t}\right) = i\hat{H}\Delta t / \hbar$$

Notice the interesting result and the major simplification. That is, in extremum energy, the equation reduces:

$$e^{(\frac{\partial g}{\partial t})} \Psi(M_\mu, t_0) \rightarrow e^{(0)} \Psi(M_\mu, t_0)$$

$$\Psi(M_\mu, t) = \Psi(M_\mu, t_0)$$

If one is correct than the only parameters which will describe at extremum are the amplitudes and the matric itself. That is to say that the motion of the Electron would be an exclusive result of the space-time configuration. Assuming lowest energy, there exist only one electron in the system, and so the spin is half integer. At ground state, the electron will act as a particle. If the electron than at that stationary state would absorb a net amount of curvature, that would result in the change in its nature.

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = \nabla^2 \neq 0$$

The new QV equation:

$$e^{\left(\frac{\partial g}{\partial t}\right)} \Psi(M_\mu, t_0) = e^{(\nabla^2)} \Psi(M_\mu, t_0)$$

$$\Psi(M_\mu, t) = e^{(\nabla^2)} \Psi(M_\mu, t_0)$$

Now the electron is not at stationary state, it absorbed a photon a net amount of curvature. Now the total spin of the system is an integer. That is given by the primorial spin formation. So at stationary state:

$$\left(2^{e^-} * \prod_{v=1}^{v=R} N_{v\mu} + (e^-)_\mu \right) \rightarrow \left(2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right)$$

With the insertion of the net curvature:

$$\left(8 * \prod_{v=1}^{v=R} N_{v\mu} + (e^-)_\mu \right) + \overline{N_{v\mu}} \rightarrow \left(2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right) + \frac{1}{2} = 30:128:850:9254 \dots$$

$$\left(2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right) + \frac{1}{2} = 128$$

Now after the electron absorbed a photon it will diverge to all directions. Since it is bounded to the nuclei it will propagate across the nuclei in all directions, as a curvature ripple. The spatial dimensions are matching the Laplace.

$$\mu = (\nabla^2, t_n, s_n)$$

The new equation can be described:

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right) \Psi(M_\mu, t) = \nabla^2 \Psi(M_\mu, t_0)$$

That is much simpler an cleaner equations than the QM ones. The solving is not included yet. The most urgent issue is crafting equations which are free of arbitrary constants as such the Planck constant and in unclear undefined terms such as $i\hbar$ and c . In here, they are not important, radical as it sounds. One last modification is that this equation must specify which arrow it belongs, which universe is it contained in.

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t_n} \right) \Psi(M_\mu, t_n) = \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x_n^2} + \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial y_n^2} + \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial z_n^2} \Psi(M_\mu, t_0) + V$$

$$t_0 \in t_n; n \in \mathbb{R}$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t_n^2} \right) \Psi(M_\mu, t_n) = \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x_n^2} + \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial y_n^2} + \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial z_n^2} \Psi(M_\mu, t_0)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 M_\mu}{\partial t_n^2} = \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x_n^2} + \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial y_n^2} + \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial z_n^2}$$

Matric via time is equal to rate of change of Ricci flow over spatial dimensions of a specific manifold. The quantum equations of Einstein general relativity:

$$g_{uv} = 8\pi T_{uv}$$

Orthogonality

That is another dominating theme in QM old formulation which needed to be shaded light upon is the subject of orthogonal states. Is there a simpler way to explain why it is important, before diving into the unclear notation of QM? This idea is used in a sense of "distinguishable states". First of all, the uses of the word "state" is too abstract, state of what? In QV all we have is the manifold. So that is much clearer. Given two distinct states of manifolds, there exist zero probability of joint union, they are disjoint.

$$\begin{aligned} \langle M_{\mu 1} | M_{\mu 2} \rangle &= 0 \\ (M_{\mu})_k &\in s; k \in \mathbb{R} \\ s &= (M, g) \end{aligned}$$

Let us examine the following equation:

$$\delta_{ij} = \begin{cases} 0 & \rightarrow i \neq j \\ 1 & \rightarrow i = j \end{cases}$$

Such does not tell anything about nature. Again it's not incorrect just badly crafted. No matter how many "important calculations" can be made with equations of that sort. What we can tell about Fermions and Bosons using the Kronecker delta? The idea of orthogonal states can be used in different manner and contexts. Below are several of those new ideas. First, orthogonality between Fermions and Bosons as an example. Alternatively, between Bosons and Bosons, that is to state that there could not be a Boson which is the inner product/average of two Bosons, that is that distinguishable Bosons are orthogonal.

$$\langle N_{V=k1} | N_{V=k2} \rangle = 0$$

It can also be used to describe the orthogonality of universes:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle s_n | s_{n+1} \rangle &= 0 ; \\ 0 &< n < K \end{aligned}$$

But here is the interesting turn of events. Since the main equation of the 8T requires:

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (2.1. A)$$

Given two distinct manifolds, which indistinguishable extremum curvatures:

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial g}{\partial t_n} \middle| \frac{\partial g}{\partial t_{n+1}} \right\rangle \neq 0$$

One must ask what is the physical implication of such an equation. It comes to an agreement with the Hamiltonian of the 8T.

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H} &= \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} + \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i + \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i \\ \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} &= \sum_{\phi=1}^K \left(\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \right)_{\phi} \end{aligned}$$

Either way 8T is providing an answer to why QM operators must be flat. The areas of extremum curvature flattening each other, causing the manifold to accelerate outward, that is basic in the 8T thesis. There is a very good chance that some, and maybe all above examples do not have a computational applications, but computation is what computers do, and it does not require thinking. Still those equations are saying something as oppose to those terms in QM that are too abstract.

Is it better to have a theory which is all-computational, not simple, impossible to imagine and full with vague terms and arbitrary numbers as the current form of QM? Alternatively, a theory which is highly simple and free of constants and un-important calculations such as 8T, which is the attempt for QM analogs using VC (Varying curvature) framework, a theory which in a sense deemed the highly important Planck constant and the speed of light as not necessary, as the coupling magnitudes are attainable without it, in a sense a theory which generate all the numbers of nature with zero measurements or effort using one algorithm.

Amplitudes

Another major subject which appears in QM formulation is the subject of amplitudes. The square of the amplitude gives a certain probability of occurrence. In relativistic QM the phases are independent from the amplitudes. The latter can be consider an as overlap. The amplitudes in QM are synonymous with energy. Now given the arrow which takes Ricci curvature to "Energy":

$$\varphi: g \rightarrow E$$

The probability of occurrence is proportional to the square of Ricci curvature, or the square of the new amplitude. assuming Ricci curvatures are constants, which will make the calculation easier to make.

$$\left(\frac{\partial g}{\partial t}\right)_{\phi=1} = 0$$

$$\left|\left(\frac{\partial g}{\partial t}\right)_{\phi=1}\right|^2 = P_{\mathbb{R}}$$

Shading light on the mechanism:

$$\int_{M_1}^{M_2} |\Psi(M_{\mu}, t_n)|^2 dM = \nabla^2 g$$

To make things more complete, in order to understand what is the probability to find a particle at 3D regions on the three dimensional matrix M_{μ} , one must compute the Ricci curvature of the system in three dimensional space, as the Ricci curvature defines the geometrical setting in which effecting the motion of the particle and thus it's potential location. As an example consider a situation where:

$$\frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x_n^2} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial y_n^2} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial z_n^2} \neq 0$$

Since the curvature does not vary in time segment on the first two spatial dimensions but only on the third, there is a major simplification and one now need to compute just one term instead of three. The particle will be found in between a range of a matrix which two set of coordinate vary only in the third spatial dimension.

In rigor, there exist a certain probability to find a particle in coordinate:

$$[x_1, y_1, z_2] \leftrightarrow [x_1, y_1, z_K]$$

$$z_K - z_2 = \Delta z$$

In other words, the probability of finding a particle is correlated to Ricci curvature configuration at time segment. The curvature orientation is dictating the probability to find a particle at a certain location. The more flat the matric, the wider the variance, and the probability to find a particle at a certain location would be equalized. Not yet computational and maybe not at all, but still a clearer version than the formulation of QM, computational as it can be. The probability to find the particle somewhere along Δz is one.

$$P(X, Y, \Delta z) = 1$$

Since reality is much complicated those are oversimplifications. In real situation we would expect:

$$P(\Delta X, \Delta Y, \Delta z) = 1$$

And we would also expect different distributions at different times. such would exclude any preferred location for the particle. The particle will aspire to reach the lowest point on the Ricci curvature, but it is not possible to tell where this point will be. Since the particle is effected by curvature ripple, which is wavelike it will move as a smoothly as a wave. This new version of QM aspires to eliminate the use of the Planck constant from those equations.

The Universe at Singularity

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t_n}\right)\Psi(M_\mu, t_n) = \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x_n^2} + \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial y_n^2} + \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial z_n^2}\Psi(M_\mu, t_0) + V\Psi$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t_n}\right)\Psi(M_\mu, t_n) = \nabla^2\Psi(M_\mu, t_0) + V\Psi$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t_n}\right)\Psi = \nabla^2\Psi + V\Psi$$

If before/at the moment of singularity, the universe had a finite size, i.e. not varying, we can require:

$$\nabla^2 = 0$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t_n}\right)\Psi = V\Psi$$

Since we require the potential energy to an entity which manifest itself as entity of the form:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$$

In addition, more recently, the potential energy of the universe was considered in the thesis:

$$U = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i + \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i$$

$$\hat{H} = \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} + \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i + \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i = \hat{T} + \hat{U}$$

At finite size, or at the singularity arrow:

$$S: t_0 \rightarrow t_0$$

Such that

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{g}}{\partial \mathbf{t}} + \sum_{i=1}^N \delta \mathbf{g}_i = 0$$

We are left with the term which is the Bosonic part of the arbitrary variation term which belong to:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta \mathbf{g}_i \subset \sum_{i=1}^N \delta \mathbf{g}_i = V$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta \mathbf{g}_i > 0$$

Such that at the moment of singularity for the manifold indexed by "n" at the time t_0 :

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t_{0(n)}} \right) \Psi = \Psi \delta \mathbf{g}_i$$

Since there is not outward acceleration, as we required finite size at the moment of t_0 to t_0 , and the manifold is still three dimensional, the arbitrary variation term on the right term is describing curvature arising from a fermion cluster and maintaining its shape. Here is term describing inner curvature composing a finite size manifold at t_0 . the manifold must appear flat, compressed. Now imagine that the term is finite, that will result in:

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t_{0(n)}} \right) \Psi = 0 \cup \Psi \delta \mathbf{g}_i = 0$$

Suppose it does vary

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t_{0(n)}} \right) \Psi = \Psi \delta \mathbf{g}_i \rightarrow \Psi \delta \mathbf{g}_i + \frac{\partial \mathbf{g}}{\partial \mathbf{t}} + \sum_{i=1}^N \delta \mathbf{g}_i$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{g}}{\partial \mathbf{t}} \neq 0$$

The flattening moment. That thing is rather abstract, as far as one can see, if one derived those equations correctly. The manifold has innate curvature at singularity that keeps it flat, finite in size, it does not accelerate thereby, and is at a state where it is only a potential curvature. At the moment of singularity the potential term varies, yielding a varying curvature on the manifold, agreeing with a varying time as it is possible to differentiate the states. Now the result of the innate curvature term varying is igniting that acceleration term to take a positive value, and the flattening moment comes with it. That is of course just an idea. Another interesting question is concerning time. Assuming the manifold does not vary until the term of potential term breaks, the manifold still exists, but not in such way that "time could pass". Same term that appear on black holes, which we associate freeze in time: $\partial \mathbf{g} / \partial \mathbf{t} = 0$. So the manifold could have existed before singularity, just not in a manner to allow time to manifest as we know it. For the arrow of time, we need $\partial \mathbf{g} / \partial \mathbf{t} \neq 0$ resulting in the primordial, net curvature appearing in distinct discrete amounts.

The problem with the singularity can be solved using the idea of **manifold spans**, that the manifold was ignited by another manifold, in which time rose earlier. The moment the manifold departed it had potential curvature which broke, caused $\partial g / \partial t \neq 0$ and the acceleration. That was also the moment the manifold inherited a unique arrow and spatial dimensions.

It is possible to imagine the manifold as a three-dimensional compressed sphere which had a non-varying state, curvature wise, for some continuous or discrete segment in time, the moment in which curvature varied ignited the acceleration and thereby the flattening moment.

QM Axioms

What really stands at the heart of the 8T that is so "hard to grasp"? The author does not think there exist such a thing. What is hard to grasp is the methods and techniques that are used to describe the reality of QM. That is the methods are the source of the problem and in particular the dominant part of LA, which is horrendous as means of **trying to imagine** what is happening. At the heart of it QM is composed of few simple Axioms which are:

- (1) The spectrum of 'Energy' is **discrete**
- (2) A physical **system** has a **set of potential arrows** leading to different results.
- (3) there exist a **chance to each arrow**. The sum of all arrows is one.
- (4) Objects are randomly generated.
- (5) Physical systems has **objects**, which are **disjoint, joint, and semi-disjoint**. That is orthogonal, identical or entangled. Distinct arrows are orthogonal.
- (6) **Time variance** of objects has an Iso-arrow to **3D spatial variance**.

Quantum Tunneling

What is the analog of tunneling using varying manifolds? Since photons can travel via matter, in a solid compact formation, and Bosons are belonging to the same class as Fermions, that is also given by the Electron and it's duality to the Boson of the weak interaction, there result of this construction is the following: matter and in particular electrons can travel via matter. A statement which is synonymous with the idea of tunneling. Now since 8T is relatively new, it is less evident to date, on how to perform the calculations on the probability of tunneling, as this framework does not have constants such as the Planck, which is used in almost all calculations In QM. Instead the author will follow reason in trying to predict.

It is possible to assume that there are several factors which effect the probability of tunneling. The first is the amount of matter which the tunneled particle should cross. The bigger it is the smaller the probability of crossing. That is assumed correct as the larger the matter count in volume, the bigger the chance the particle would be 'trapped' or pulled onto one on the nucleons. The second element is the tunneled particle energy, which is proportional to momenta. The higher the energy, the bigger the momenta, the particle diverges faster and thus will go via the matter cluster in faster pace, which will decrease the chance of being trapped in the matter liar. There exist another option concerning tunneling, which involves the idea of identical particles. If one had an electron in region, which was destroyed by pairing it with the positron and in the mean time, the liar of nucleons propagated from within it a distinct electron, which now is outside the region, since the two Electrons are manifested by the same number, it is impossible to distinguish them. One can conclude that the Electron crossed the barrier.

$$\left(2_{\mu}^{e^{-}} * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + e^{-}_{\mu} \right) \in [A, B]$$

$$e^{+}_{\mu} \in [A, B]$$

$$e^{-}_{\mu} + e^{+}_{\mu} \in [A, B] = 0$$

$$2_{\mu}^{e^{-}} \rightarrow e^{-}_{\mu 1} \in [C, D]$$

$$e^{-}_{\mu 1} \equiv e^{-}_{\mu}$$

$$[C, D] \notin [A, B]$$

Because of the Electron duality to the Boson of the weak interaction, any feature which is related to the class of Boson, should be inherited by the Lepton. This version of Boson Fermion duality is by the primordial second term, which is the most symmetrical.

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 \dots$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3$$

$$3 \equiv (3)$$

$$(e)^{-} = W^{-}$$

We can define the inheritance conduction by equalizing the classes. The Fermion class are of vanishing curvature spikes and the Electron. The Bosonic class are discrete prime amount of curvature, which are non- vanishing, and the Electron. The Electron is the unique term that belong to both classes.

$$\mathbb{F}_{class} = \{2n \cup e^{-} | (2n \cap e^{-}) \in s\}$$

$$\mathbb{B}_{class} = \{\mathbb{P} \cup (+1) | (\mathbb{P} \cup (+1)) \in s\}$$

$$s = (M_{E}, g) \leftarrow (3,1)$$

O Manor

$$\mathbb{F}_{class} \cap \mathbb{B}_{class} = e^-$$

$$e^- \equiv (3) \in \mathbb{P}$$

The unique term that belong to both classes must exhibit the features of both classes. That insight was known long before 8T was crafted. However, the primorial validates and shade light on way those things are correct. It does so in such a simple fashion, compared to QFT which has to go via SUSY to reach the insight of alignment at 26 variations.

The Atom

$$(\delta g_1 \delta g_1 \delta g_1)$$

$$(\delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_2)$$

$$(\delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_1)$$

$$(\delta g_1 \delta g_1 \delta g_2)$$

$$(\delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_1)$$

$$(\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_2)$$

$$(\delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_2)$$

$$(\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1)$$

$$(\delta g_3 \delta g_3 \delta g_3)$$

The pairing of atoms is such that inverse threefold combinations pairs.

$$(\delta g_3 \delta g_3 \delta g_3)$$

$$(\delta g_1 \delta g_1 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_2)$$

$$(\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_2) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_1)$$

$$(\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_2)$$

$$(\delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_1 \delta g_1 \delta g_2)$$

That is due to the conditions of stationarity on the Lorentz manifold. The order of the pairing is not evident in the 8T, as the author did not consider it relevant at that point. The physics is was important in that context back in the day, while the 8T was still in early stages of construction. Now emphasis will be made on the formation of atoms. Since the pairing of each threefold is incomplete in a sense that not all threefold combination bring an element to itself:

$$(\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_2)$$

That element will pair to another threefold combination that is imperfect and include the inverse signs. That is synonymous with the process of just two arbitrary variations vanishing to zero, given by the stationarity condition. It is possible to examine the threefold combinations in terms of edges. Those edges will pull another threefold combinations, thereby creating elements with heavier Hadrons, i.e. large number of Hadron composites.

$$(\delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_2) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_2) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1)$$

And all of those formations are due to the condition of stationary manifold.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$$

Another important note is the following. The most stable state in the set of the threefold combinations must be the lowest with the lowest energy. Since we had the mapping from Ricci curvature to energy, the most stable threefold combination must be most flat. Now another point which is important is the following. It is impossible to associate to each threefold combination different degrees of curvature, i.e. energy. The threefold combination does not tell how volatile are the arbitrary amount of curvature. To demonstrate:

$$(\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1) \rightarrow E_{121}^{\mathcal{L}_0}$$

$$(\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1) \rightarrow E_{121}^{\mathcal{L}_1}$$

$$E_{121}^{\mathcal{L}_0} \neq E_{121}^{\mathcal{L}_1}$$

Such a construction will allow us to indicate that the direction of development would be as such that threefold combination will aspire lowest energy state. That is in agreement with 8T idea of emission of the electron. And it is also similar to the Quantum formulation of subscript and superscript on the electron, to indicate his aspiration to reach lowest energy state. We can make the transformation between energy state of threefold combinations.

$$E_{121}^{\mathcal{L}_1} = E_{121}^{\mathcal{L}_0} + e^-$$

Using that idea it is also possible to solidify the direction of the families formation. As the manifold develops, i.e. accelerates due to being a part of the packet, flatter and flatter combinations should rise. That means lower and lower masses. In the 8T, the Quark masses pattern indicate to that direction, i.e. third family is the first and first family is the third.

$$19,600 \rightarrow 1400 \rightarrow 56$$

$$176,400 \rightarrow 1400 \rightarrow 6.3 \rightarrow 0.113 \rightarrow$$

Using those theoretical insights it is possible to reason for the similarity of the generations, they are the class of arbitrary variations, which differ in their level intensity. The latter is proportional to the arrow of time.

Immense Spin Formations

$$\begin{aligned}
 &(\delta g_3 \delta g_3 \delta g_3) \\
 &(\delta g_1 \delta g_1 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_2) \\
 &(\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_2) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_1) \\
 &(\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_2) \\
 &(\delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_1 \delta g_1 \delta g_2) \\
 &(\delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_2) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_2) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1) \\
 &(\delta g_1 \delta g_1 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_2) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_1 \delta g_1 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_2) \\
 &(\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_2) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_2) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_2)
 \end{aligned}$$

Using the endless clustering of matter, i.e. construction of the periodic time table, which will eventually yield a proportional number of electrons as each of those threefold combination will and can emit an electron given by the primordial.

$$(\delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_2) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_2) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1) \rightarrow Ke^-$$

$$K \in \mathbb{R}$$

Since those electron has spin, given the second form of the primordial, the immense cluster of electrons and therefore the Bosons they emit contain spin as well. The summation of spin must be valid in large-scale formation of matter, i.e. arbitrary variations of the manifold, which takes the form of threefold combinations of two distinct elements, which differ in sign and summed as zero, or thanks to the contributions of physicists, Quarks. The large formation of matter must posses spin, or angular momenta around a self-Axis. The spin summation is due to the contribution of Electrons and Bosons in the cluster.

$$\begin{aligned}
 S &= \sum_{i=0}^N e^- + \sum_{k=1}^N Z_k \sum_{k=1}^N N_{V_k} \\
 S &\in \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0
 \end{aligned}$$

The two-fold summation reason is the following. One must sum across the kind of Bosons in play inside the matter cluster. Such a construction allow one to make a prediction:

- (1) All mega scale Fermion formations, stars and galaxies must have spin. The matter spirals of galaxies should spin around the axis of the center of galaxy and stars should spin around a self-axis taken from pole to pole.

Gravity within Fermion Clusters

$$\begin{aligned}
 &(\delta g_3 \delta g_3 \delta g_3) \\
 &(\delta g_1 \delta g_1 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_2) \\
 &(\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_2) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_1) \\
 &(\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_2) \\
 &(\delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_1 \delta g_1 \delta g_2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^L e^- = e^-_1 + e^-_2 + \dots + e^-_L$$

At any given time an heavy element which has two "clouds of probability", i.e. electrons, and those electron propagate on a common segment, there exist a chance those the Electrons will emit a discrete amount of net curvature at the same time. That spatial alignment and temporal alignment will result in the Graviton. That nature of the composition given by the spin two trait, is what makes the Graviton short range.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left(2e^- * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + (e^-)_{\mu} + (e^-)_{\mu} \right) + N_{V1\mu} + N_{V2\mu} = 2N_0 + 2 \\
 &(N_{V2\mu} \equiv N_{V1\mu}) \cup (N_{V2\mu} \neq N_{V1\mu})
 \end{aligned}$$

The only condition one is requiring is the five vector to be aligned, that the ripples will interest, both on the spatial and temporal. Since both contain the Laplacian in the five vector, and time as well, it is important to align all the elements on the five vector. Than the decay of the Graviton can be put as two Photons/or any two Bosons and two Electrons.

$$(e^-)_{\mu} + (e^-)_{\mu} + N_{V1\mu} + N_{V2\mu} \leftrightarrow G$$

Thus the Graviton may likely be rising at large scale Fermion formations, where there exit immense amount of Leptons which may emit together, yielding an higher spin particle, such as the Graviton. In the 8T, for those reasons has infinite combinations. Gravity, i.e. curvature is the class, where different objects, given by the primorial are rising. The interaction among starts than is taking place by long range mediator such as light, which is represented by one independent term of prime.

Threefold Binders

$$\begin{aligned}
 &(\delta g_3 \delta g_3 \delta g_3) \\
 &(\delta g_1 \delta g_1 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_2) \\
 &(\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_2) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_1) \\
 &(\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_2) \\
 &(\delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_1 \delta g_1 \delta g_2)
 \end{aligned}$$

Imagine that a threefold combination could break to a certain spatial coordinate, its matched pair is breaking to another spatial coordinate, that is a violation of stationarity on the manifold.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \neq 0$$

Within each threefold combination, there must be than at least by reason a threefold binder. The nature of the threefold binder is related to the size of the prime paring, given by theorems two and three of the 8T. for the threefold binder the element is represented by $N_{V1\mu} = +1$. Those threefold binders are net curvature on the manifold. Each net is increasing the chance of another net to arrive to its position. The result an endless succession of net curvature converging toward the threefold combination, or a "sea of Gluons", which ensures the trapped nature of the two distinct elements.

$$(\delta g_1^{(\leftrightarrow)} \delta g_1^{(\leftrightarrow)} \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2^{(\leftrightarrow)} \delta g_2^{(\leftrightarrow)} \delta g_2)$$

$$(\leftrightarrow) = \sum_{i=1}^K g_i = +1 + 1 + 1 \dots$$

Curvature scattering by matter

Within a threefold combination we assumed there exist a sea of threefold binders. That is given by the term:

$$(\delta g_1^{(\leftrightarrow)} \delta g_1^{(\leftrightarrow)} \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2^{(\leftrightarrow)} \delta g_2^{(\leftrightarrow)} \delta g_2)$$

Imagine the following scenario in which higher coupling Boson is propagating directly into matter. Since the threefold combination is emitting the Lepton and the Lepton is responsible for the Boson emissions, it is possible to assume that for the higher coupling Boson will not penetrate directly but rather by scattered by the threefold combination.

$$N_{V1\mu} \rightarrow (\delta g_1^{(\leftrightarrow)} \delta g_1^{(\leftrightarrow)} \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2^{(\leftrightarrow)} \delta g_2^{(\leftrightarrow)} \delta g_2) \searrow N_{V1\mu}$$

It is getting interesting, it is possible to assume that the higher term Boson did get in to the threefold cluster, and the scattered Boson is composed by the same amount of distinct elements. such that the photon which came in, is not the photon which came out, but five net curvature which were in the original Fermion.

$$\searrow N_{V\mu} = \sum_{i=1}^5 g_i = +1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1$$

Curvature Subsets

The subset condition, for any fermion cluster we have, which Bosons propagate within it, by the three critical theorems of the 8T, we have that the Bosonic class is a subset of the Fermion cluster. That is the:

$$\sum_{k=1}^N Z_k \sum_{k=1}^N N_{V_k} \subset \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \right)$$

